

**PROCEDURE OF ACCESSION TO THE EUROPEAN UNION
(COPENHAGEN AND MADRID CRITERIA): COMPARATIVE
ANALYSIS WITH THE UNITED NATIONS ORGANIZATION AND
OTHER INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS**

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Annotation: This article examines the procedure for joining the European Union and the legal aspects of accession provided for by the Maastricht Agreement, as well as the Copenhagen and Madrid criteria. Using the example of some countries, an analysis of the nuances of the process of accession to the European Union is carried out. Also, recommendations are made to improve and change the Copenhagen criteria, which may have lost their relevance today. Further, the article details the step-by-step procedure for accession and provides a comparative analysis between the process of accession to the United Nations and the process of accession to the European Union.

Key words: European Union law, Copenhagen and Madrid criteria, *acquis communautaire*, international organizations, enlargement and accession to international organizations.

Introduction

The European Union enlargement process is a long process of accession to the organization of new States. The process began in 1952, by the unification of the inner six who founded the Coal and Steel Community, the predecessor of the European Union. The inner six consisted of following States such as Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg and the Netherlands.¹

With this event began the unification that encompassed more and more European countries. As can be seen from the chronology, the initial purpose of unification was purely economic. Then, further unifications also included the political aspect from the point of view of security within the union. At this point,

¹Bernard Stirn, “The Phases of European Integration”, *Towards a European Public Law* (Oxford University Press, 2017), p.25.

the process is strictly regulated by legal specifics, which will be discussed in this article.

The process of enlargement of the European Union is sometimes referred as the “European integration”.² The meaning of the same: the process of strengthening interstate relations by uniting into a single international organization. At this stage, the legal aspect plays a key role, as cooperation between states takes place by harmonizing the law of member-states.

Conditions of accession

The first thing that should be noted is the requirements under the Maastricht Treaty (Treaty on European Union), according to which all member-states of the European Union, as well as the European Parliament, must come to a unanimous agreement for the accession of a new state. Thus, according to Article 49 of the Maastricht Treaty:

“Any European State which respects the values referred to in Article 2 and seeks to promote them may apply to join the Union. The European Parliament and the national parliaments shall be notified of this application. The applicant State shall forward its application to the Council, which shall take a unanimous decision after consulting the Commission and obtaining the consent of the European Parliament, which shall act by a majority of its constituent members. The conditions of admissibility agreed by the European Council shall be taken into account.

The conditions of acceptance and the modifications to the Treaties on which the Union is based which such acceptance entails shall be the subject of an agreement between the Member States and the applicant State. This Agreement shall be submitted for ratification to all Contracting States in accordance with their constitutional requirements”.³

As it is stated in Article 49(1) of the Maastricht Treaty, the conditions of admissibility agreed by the European Council must be taken into account.

Copenhagen and Madrid criteria

These requirements are set out in the opinion of the President of the Council of Europe on the Copenhagen Conference held on June 21 and 22, 1993. According to Article 7, paragraph 3 of these conclusions, Central and Eastern European countries wishing to join the Union and meeting the political and economic criteria may apply.

The conditions of accession for a candidate country are as follows:

² Jo Show, European Integration, (Oxford Public International Law, 2022), p.1.

³Treaty on European Union 1992, Article 49.

- stability of institutions guaranteeing democracy, rule of law, human rights, respect and protection of minorities,
- the existence of a functioning market economy able to cope with competitive pressures and market forces within the country,
- the ability of the candidate to assume the obligations of membership, including a commitment to the objectives of political, economic and monetary union.
- the Union's ability to accept new members while maintaining the momentum of European integration is also an important factor in the common interest of both the Union and the candidate countries.⁴

In case of fulfillment of these criteria, which will be assessed by the European Council unanimously with the Commission and the Parliament, the state may become a member of the European Union.

The above criteria were amended by the Madrid Conference held by the Council of Europe in December 1995. According to these changes, another important criterion was the conformity of the administrative structure to implement the existing laws of the candidate country.⁵

As noted above, for membership in the European Union, it is important that a country's national legislation conforms to the standards of the European Union. This process is referred to as *acquis communautaire*, which implies that potential members must harmonize their legislation with European laws.⁶ However, the existence of legislation alone is not enough. For their implementation, as noted in the Madrid meetings, the existence of an appropriate administration in the state is necessary.

We believe that the standards for entry into the European Union under the Copenhagen criteria were high. The changes to the Madrid criteria have made the bar even higher. This makes further integration of the European Union even more difficult. For example, Turkey first applied in 2005 and the application is still pending.⁷ Both economic and political aspects were considered when deciding on Turkey's entry into the European Union. Only in assessing the level of democratization in the country, i.e. the political aspect, the following issues have been considered and conclusions have been made by the Commission:

- 1) *Parliament* - accession to the Covenant on Political and Civil Rights, the Covenant on Social and Economic Rights, the primacy of international law

⁴Declaration of European Union 1993.

⁵Declaration of European Union 1995.

⁶ Heather Grabbe, European Union Conditionality and the “*Acquis Communautaire*”, Vol.23 No.3, p.5

⁷https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/enlargement-policy/turkiye_en

- over national law, amendments to the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Codes;
- 2) *Administrative measures* - introduction of monitoring for the protection of human rights;
 - 3) *Legal and judicial system* - independence of the judiciary and ensuring measures to combat torture;
 - 4) *Corruption* - accession to the Convention on Combating Corruption;
 - 5) Accession to human rights conventions;
 - 6) Abolition of the death penalty as a punishment; Prohibition of torture;
 - 7) Freedom of expression, association and religion;
 - 8) Protection of women's rights –enforcing gender equality policies;
 - 9) Protection children's rights;
 - 10) Protection of the rights of religious and national minorities.

Since Turkey did not meet the above criteria, its accession to the European Union is on hold as a candidate.⁸ As stated in the Copenhagen Resolution of 2002, the political and economic criteria must already be met in order to start the accession negotiation process. Let us consider the accession procedure itself.

EU accession procedure

As mentioned above, the first step to join the Union is to apply to the Council, followed by the conclusion of the Association Agreement. The EU Council asks the EU Commission to initiate the negotiation process. After receiving a response, the Council either agrees or rejects the opinion of the EU Commission. The next process is the process of negotiations. According to the EU Commission's report, the Council decides whether the applicant state is a candidate state. If so, the Council starts negotiating the “chapters” of the law. Negotiating the “chapters” means that the candidate state has to revise its legislation and bring it in line with the standards of the European Union. During the negotiations, several chapters are opened and an annual report on the adopted changes is kept. This is the process of *acquires communautaire*. If the process is successful, a European Union accession agreement is signed, which must be ratified by all members of the European Union.

This is the procedure that exists today. Over time, both the Copenhagen and Madrid conditions may change. Researchers have proposed to revise the Copenhagen criteria and introduce a new format called Copenhagen Plus.⁹ This

⁸ Erich Hochleitner, Working Paper, Austrian Institute for European Security Policy August 2005, p.20.

⁹E.Pachulidze&R.Youngs, *Beyond the Copenhagen Criteria: Rethinking the Political Conditions of EU Accession*.

format means that in the pre-accession period special attention should be paid to the development of civil society. The European Union, in turn, should create a fund to support the institution of civil society, while the state should provide attention to the development of this institution. Thus, a new criterion is added to the Copenhagen Principles: a developed civil society in the state.

Also, in November 2019, France proposed a seven-stage EU accession plan. The reformed accession strategy involves participation in various programs such as Erasmus, Banking Union, Capital Markets Union, and Customs Union.¹⁰ It follows that the process of joining the European Union is complicated not only by legal and economic criteria, but also the importance of internal political relations with each of the members of the European Union, which may not want to enlarge the organization.

Procedure of joining the UN

The procedure of accession of states to the United Nations is much easier with the procedure of accession to the European Union. According to the UN Charter, any peace-loving state that is ready to fulfill the obligations under the Charter can join the Organization. The procedure is as follows:

1. Submitting application to the Secretary General;
2. The Secretary General submits the application to the UN Security Council, with 9 out of 15 members voting in favor and the decision must not be vetoed by the permanent members;
3. Upon the recommendation of the Security Council, the General Assembly votes with an agenda on the accession of the state in question to the organization. At least 2/3 of the members of the states of the General Assembly must vote in favor. The decision shall enter into force from the moment of signing the Resolution.

The process of joining the UN is not complicated, unlike the European Union. This is due to the fact that the goals of joining these organizations are significantly different. If the purpose of joining the UN is to be recognized in the international arena, as a state and in general the ability to enter into international relations, then in the European Union the situation is slightly different. States join the European Union for narrower political considerations, such as ensuring security and establishing friendly relations with neighboring states. Another aspect is economic, such as joining a free economic zone and opening migration borders. Consequently, since the accession of each state to

¹⁰<https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/ru/politique-etrangere/la-france-et-l-europe/l-union-europeenne/la-presidence-francaise-du-conseil-de-l-union-europeenne/>

the European Union is fraught with consequences, the established requirements are difficult to be met in a short period of time. Moreover, some members of the European Union may further complicate the process with their anti-enlargement policies.

Thus, the process of accession to the European Union, from the point of view of law, it is the harmonization of national law with the established European standards. Without proper ensuring of the rule of law, respect for human rights and freedoms, as well as without appropriate administration in the state, according to the Copenhagen and Madrid criteria, the accession process is impossible. Since the revision of the entire legal system is impossible in the shortest possible time, many states are either denied accession or are still in a waiting status. The positive side of these envisaged rules is definitely the improvement of respect for human rights and the achievement of due legal development of the state.

References:

1. D. Chalmers, G. Davies, G. Monti, & V. Heyvaert, European Union law: Text and Materials 5th ed. (Cambridge University Press, 2024);
2. J. Klabbers, International Law 4th ed. (Cambridge University Press, 2023);
3. B. Stirn, "The Phases of European Integration", Towards a European Public Law (Oxford University Press, 2017);
4. J. Show, European Integration, (Oxford Public International Law, 2022);
5. H. Grabbe, European Union Conditionality and the "Acquis Communautaire", Vol.23 No.3;
6. E. Hochleitner, Working Paper, Austrian Institute for European Security Policy August 2005;
7. E. Pachulidze & R. Youngs, Beyond the Copenhagen Criteria: Rethinking the Political Conditions of EU Accession;
8. J. Palmowski, Copenhagen Criteria. In A Dictionary of Contemporary World History (Oxford University Press, 2024).
9. Treaty on European Union 1992;
10. Declaration of European Council in Copenhagen 1993;
11. Declaration of European Council in Madrid 1995.

